

Amortised inference in diffusion MRI biophysical models using artificial neural networks and simulation-based frameworks

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Synopsis

Inference in imaging-based biophysical modelling provides a principled way of estimating model parameters, but also assessing confidence/uncertainty on results, quantifying noise effects and aiding experimental design. Traditional approaches in neuroimaging can either be very computationally expensive (e.g., Bayesian) or suitable to only certain assumptions (e.g., bootstrapping). We present a simulation-based inference approach to estimate diffusion MRI model parameters and their uncertainty. This novel framework trains a neural network to learn a Bayesian model inversion, allowing inference for unseen data. Results show a high level of agreement with conventional Markov-Chain-Monte-Carlo estimates, while offering 2-3 orders of magnitude speed-ups and inference amortisation.

Summary of Main Findings

Simulation-based inference can use artificial neural networks to provide equivalent model estimates to classical Bayesian inference while providing massive computational speedups and opening new opportunities for likelihood-free inference problems.

Abstract

Introduction

Inference and uncertainty quantification in imaging-based modelling provides a principled way of estimating non-linear model parameters, but also assessing confidence on results (1), quantifying noise effects (2) and aiding experimental design (3). In diffusion MRI (dMRI), it can assess precision of tissue microstructure estimates, while allowing probabilistic estimation of white-matter tracts (2). Traditional approaches for inference and uncertainty quantification include iterative bootstrapping (4) or Bayesian inference (5, 6). However, given the high data dimensionality with modern dMRI protocols (e.g., (7)), the large space of parameters and/or the lack of tractable likelihoods in some cases, traditional approaches can be slow, computationally demanding or, directly, unusable.

Simulation-based inference (SBI) uses forward models to provide a data-driven alternative to classical inference based on training an artificial neural network (ANN) to learn posterior distributions (or approximate likelihoods), avoiding the requirement of likelihood inversions. We present here a first application of SBI in voxel-wise microstructural modelling and uncertainty quantification for dMRI data.

Methods

We designed an SBI framework for a dMRI biophysical model and compared it against a classical Bayesian inference approach, the Markov-Chain-Monte-Carlo (MCMC). In both approaches, our goal is to estimate the posterior distribution of the model parameters θ given data x , $P(\theta|x) \sim P(x|\theta)P(\theta)$ (Fig.1). In classical inference, this is done by inverting the forward model using approximate/iterative approaches, like MCMC. In SBI, this is achieved by training an ANN to learn the mapping between parameters and the data, using training datasets simulated from the forward model $f_x(\theta)$. This subsequently allows inference of the posterior given new data from the trained network directly, without model inversion (amortised inference).

SBI can be casted as a problem of *neural density estimation* (Fig.2A). A parametric model Q_ϕ , that takes as inputs pairs of datapoints (u, v) , returns a conditional probability density $Q_\phi(u|v)$ that is an approximation to the true conditional density $P(u|v)$. This can be chosen to be any conditional density distribution, e.g., likelihood or posterior; when estimating the posterior it is known as Neural Posterior Estimator (NPE) (9).

Using an artificial neural network as the parametric model, and the simulator $f_x(\theta)$ to create a simulated training dataset $\{\theta_N, x_N\}$, we can train $Q_\phi(\theta|x)$ by maximizing the total log probability, $\sum_N \log Q_\phi(\theta_N|x_N)$, with respect to hyper-parameters ϕ (9). To obtain distributions rather than point estimates, conditional density estimators are usually embedded into the ANN, with Normalizing Flows one of the most flexible options (10). Importantly, the learnt model allows for amortised inference (Fig.2B), i.e., to automatically infer parameters and their uncertainty for new unseen data, instead of going through a numerical model inversion process again for each new dataset as in classical model fitting.

Without loss of generality, we evaluated the above framework using the Ball&Sticks model as an exemplar for $f_x(\theta)$. We generated data ($b=1000$ s/mm², 64 directions), and we firstly optimised the NPE hyper-parameters. We explored a range of possible density estimators (MDN, MADE (11, 12), MAF (13), and NSF (14)), convergence depending on training data size, and parameter priors. Using the best configuration, we compared the SBI and the MCMC results in both simulated and real data. For all the experiments, we used the *sbi* Python toolbox (15), and we implemented a random-walk Metropolis-Hastings MCMC in Python.

Results

Hyperparameter Optimisation

Using the absolute percentage error between SBI estimates and ground-truth values in 1000 numerically-generated datasets as agreement criterion, the Neural Spline Flow (NSF) (14) showed the best performance compared to the other density estimators (Fig.3A). We also found that using uniforms showed more stable results and faster convergence than using Gamma distributions for diffusivity (Fig.3B). Finally, we have found that using a set of $N=10^6$ training dMRI datasets was enough for the network to converge while keeping an affordable training time (Fig.3D).

Comparisons to MCMC – Numerically-generated data

We generated 1000 synthetic datasets with parameters varying as follows: $d:[0-5e-3$ mm²/s], $f:[0-1]$, orientations: $[\alpha:0-\pi; \beta:0-2\pi$ rads], SNR: $[5-50]$. The scatter plots shown in Fig. 4B, 4C show the mean estimates obtained by MCMC and SBI, compared to ground-truth for these configurations and for different SNR levels. Both approaches provided accurate estimates, with accuracy slightly reducing for lower SNR as expected.

Comparisons to MCMC – Real brain data

In this case, the SBI estimates are compared directly to the MCMC outputs. There is a high level of agreement in mean estimates between both approaches (Fig.5A, B, C). (16)The tract bundles obtained by running XTRACT (16) (i.e., probabilistic tractography) using the fibre orientations provided by SBI also show a high correlation with those obtained from the MCMC approach.

Computational performance

In a single-CPU core, the training of the network required 113 hours. Inference for every new whole-brain unseen dataset (104x104x56 voxels) took ~10 minutes. Running MCMC took more than 100 hours for each dataset. This reflects a speed-up of 2-3 orders of magnitude in parameter inference once the network is trained.

Conclusion

We have provided a first demonstration of SBI in dMRI microstructural modelling. The SBI framework provides higher flexibility and major advantages in terms of computational efficiency with respect to classical approaches, such as the MCMC, while keeping the accuracy of estimation.

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Figures

MCMC

Iterative inference process. For each x_i :

SBI

Fig. 1. Flow diagram comparison - Similarities (orange) and differences (blue) between SBI and MCMC. While in the MCMC the inference process is repeated k times for every voxel v , in SBI we simulate N measurements $X = \{x_i\}$ with $i = 1 \dots N$, to train a model. This learnt model allows for amortised inference so it can be used to automatically infer the approximated posterior of the parameters for new data X .

Fig. 2. Simulation-based inference framework - A. Using the priors $P(\theta)$, we can produce parameter proposals θ_i , simulate the correspondent dMRI dataset x_i and use it to train the NPE, that contains the Normalizing Flows embedded, to provide an approximated posterior density $Q_\phi(\hat{\theta}_i | x_i)$. **B.** The learnt posterior density $Q_\phi(\hat{\theta}_i | x_i)$ is amortised, i.e., if it is trained correctly, it can be used to infer the posterior density of parameters for any new observation x_{i_new} .

Fig. 3. Hyper-parameters optimisation - % absolute error between SBI estimates and ground-truth ($N=1000$ simulated datasets): *A* comparison between *A.* different density estimators, and *B.* different diffusivity priors, $P(d)$. *C.* Examples of posterior probability distributions returned for a single observation. *D.* Training metrics: time vs training size (red) and $\log(\text{probability})$ in the validation set vs training size (green).

Fig. 4. Simulated data results – Comparison of MCMC (orange) and SBI (blue). *A.* f_1 posterior distributions returned by the MCMC and SBI in a single dataset example. *B.* *C.* Scatter plot of MCMC and SBI estimates compared to the ground-truth of mean diffusivity d (*B*) and volume fraction (*C*) for low and high SNR levels.

Fig. 5. Brain data results – Estimated mean maps using MCMC (left column) and SBI (middle column) for the diffusivity *d* (A), volume fraction *f1* (B) and fibre orientation (C). The right column shows the scatter plot of the MCMC and SBI estimates for *d* and *f1*, and a histogram of the fibre orientation difference expressed in angle degrees. **D.** Probabilistic tractography of white matter tracts (axial and coronal views).